

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Journal of Rural Studies

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/jrurstud

Empowering farmers to conserve grassland's genetic diversity *in situ*

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

In situ program
Grassland
Farmers
ECA
AES
Crop wild relatives
Motivation

ABSTRACT

The genetic diversity of grassland species is increasingly at risk due to agricultural intensification, habitat fragmentation, and climate change, which increase the vulnerability of ecosystems to pests and diseases. Protecting this diversity is critical for the resilience of agricultural systems, yet current agri-environmental schemes often struggle to halt genetic erosion. Their effectiveness depends not only on policy design but also on farmers' willingness and motivation to participate.

This study investigates the factors shaping farmers' participation in a newly established voluntary scheme in Switzerland, the "*in situ* program," which aims to conserve the genetic diversity of fodder plants and their wild relatives on semi-intensive grasslands. Drawing on national eco-geographical data combined with an online farmer survey, we analysed participation patterns through the lens of the Theory of Planned Behaviour.

Our results show that participating farms are typically larger, located at higher altitudes, and more likely to hold organic certification. Beyond structural factors, voluntary participation fostered intrinsic motivation and enhanced farmers' appreciation of their role in conserving agrobiodiversity.

We conclude that successful agro-environmental policies must recognize farmers as active custodians of genetic resources and support their engagement through schemes that combine ecological objectives with the values and motivations of farming communities.

1. Introduction

Preserving genetic diversity in agroecosystems is essential for keeping agriculture resilient in the face of rising threats such as new pests and diseases, drought, and climate change acceleration (Hajjar et al., 2008; Khoury et al., 2022). Conservation of agrobiodiversity has been addressed in a vast diversity of ways and methods by policy makers, with an estimated 6000 agri-environmental policies having been used since the 1960s (Matthies et al., 2023). Europe is by far the most policy-rich region in addressing agrobiodiversity loss. Agroenvironmental schemes (AES) have been central elements of multifunctional agriculture, which promotes diverse farming systems that integrate multiple crops, livestock, and ecological functions. More generally, it helps to conserve genetic resources, enhance ecosystem resilience, and reduce reliance on monocultures and industrial inputs (Renting et al., 2009). Unfortunately, more than thirty years after the deployment of multifunctional agriculture and its derived AES, the biodiversity loss has not

reversed (Mace et al., 2018; Leclère et al., 2020), agriculture-related habitats are still threatened, and many farms' sustainability remains fragile (Klebl et al., 2024). Understandably, some criticism has been raised against these policies, which are sometimes considered unambitious, lacking effectiveness and efficiency (Pe'er et al., 2022). The link between the quality of the AES implementation, which is supposed to translate into sustainable agricultural practice and, in turn, improve biodiversity conservation, is complex and has been the focus of extensive work (Canessa et al., 2024; Dessart et al., 2019; Home et al., 2014; Klebl et al., 2024; Schaub et al., 2023).

A peculiarity of the Swiss landscape is the high proportion of grasslands (pastures and meadows), making up about 60 % of the 606'000 ha of agricultural land. Grasslands, as a primary source of forage are under particular pressure. Conserving grassland involves both protecting native genetic diversity and maintaining a gene pool important for forage plant breeding (Hammond et al., 2004; Moroder and Kernecker, 2022; Westerink et al., 2024). Grasses (*Poaceae*) and legumes

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.103938>

Received 8 April 2025; Received in revised form 8 September 2025; Accepted 16 November 2025

Available online 20 November 2025

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(*Fabaceae*) are actively bred for yields, digestibility, and disease resistance (Capstaff and Miller, 2018). However, the ability of forage crop breeders to produce viable crops strongly depends on their access to the diversity of wild relatives of these crops in meadows and pastures (Kägi et al., 2023). Most AES are actively trying to maintain this diversity of plants, but without specifically focusing on forage crops and their wild relatives.

Almost 20 % of the Swiss agricultural surface is engaged in agro-environmental schemes. Ecological compensation areas (ECAs) are declared across the whole country, with significant differences between altitudes (46 % of ECAs in high mountain zones), farm types and quality achieved (FOAG, 2023). Most agro-environmental subsidies follow cross-compliance principles, where subsidies are conditioned to particular actions, results or multi-actor collaborations (Aviron et al., 2009). A large portion of the ECAs are extensive meadows and pastures (FOAG, 2023). A two-tiered subsidy system guarantees that proof of ecological performance is provided. Following legal guidelines from the national agriculture policy, basic quality surfaces (referred to as “quality I”) prescribe minimal actions for biodiversity upon subsidy payment. Besides this basic level, result-based measures (referred to as “quality II surfaces” with *post hoc* controls of the floristic quality achieved) enable the management of surfaces or fields that have an enhanced potential for biodiversity. At the top of these two tiers, a collaborative scheme targeting landscape-level biodiversity (i.e. multiple farms involved) and gathering multiple farms allows for addressing other trophic levels, such as birds and butterflies (Meier et al., 2021, 2024). In these high-quality surfaces, a list of keystone species defined *ex ante* by the authorities is meant to provide a proxy for the state of biodiversity. These subsidies, while considered relatively efficient (Kampmann et al., 2012), are mainly predefined “top-down” decisions made independently of farmers and before the programme’s implementation. The consequences of such design on the motivation of the farmers to participate and the actual efficiency of the instrument for conservation remain unclear (Riley et al., 2018). Given the relatively modest impact of cross-compliance schemes on the state of agrobiodiversity (Pe’er et al., 2022), a substantial body of work has explored whether the low impact was due to low commitment and/or low levels of compliance (Schaub et al., 2023). Beyond the simplistic view of economic rationality, a complex pattern of reasons, often context-specific, leads to farmers’ participation in an AES

(Klebl et al., 2024; Schaub et al., 2023).

In an effort to “make farmers matter” (De Snoo et al., 2013), a new policy instrument has been introduced in Switzerland in 2021 dedicated to the *in situ* conservation of forage crops (hereafter the “*in situ* program” (ISP), Kägi et al., 2023). The ISP targets surfaces that are not classified as ECA but have a considerable representation of the genetic diversity of forage crops (Fig. 1, Kägi et al., 2023). The ISP primarily focuses on 17 target species that are related to forage crop breeding (Kägi et al., 2023). Participation in the ISP is voluntary and limited in size (2 ha/farm): farmers can answer local public authority calls, which will, in turn, evaluate the surfaces to allocate the subsidies to the best ones. In exchange for the contribution, farmers must keep their surfaces intact and available for the breeders (Kägi et al., 2023). Approximately 1600 ha of quality surfaces could be secured under the ISP three years after its inception (Fig. 1).

More research is necessary to understand how to improve the design of this instrument and the resulting compliance. A farmer’s motivation to participate in an AES is central to its success in promoting agrobiodiversity-related practices (De Snoo et al., 2013). Given the novelty of the ISP program, the motivations for farmers to participate are insufficiently understood, which hinders conclusions about effective ways to encourage participation. Our study aims to identify the participants in the ISP and the underlying motivations of farmers to join the program.

We combined two approaches: we first performed an analysis of the meta-data of farms from the national agricultural census. Then we conducted an online survey targeting farmers whose surfaces were eligible for the ISP program. We analysed the farmer’s motivation through the lenses of the theory of planned behaviour (TPB, Ajzen, 1991), a theoretical framework that structures the motivation of farmers in three main components: attitudes framing the behaviour, subjective norms that may influence that behaviour, and perceived behavioural controls. We clarify the relationship between motivations, behaviours and the actual output of the ISP. The TPB is extensively used and adapted in the context of farmers’ decision-making (Home et al., 2014). The Swiss case is particularly well documented, and the TPB was successfully used to analyse farmers’ motivations (Gabel et al., 2018a; Home et al., 2014; Stoeckli et al., 2017). Based on this analysis, we evaluate the extent to which this program is well integrated into the complex

Fig. 1. The current distribution of the *in situ* surfaces across Switzerland (red dots). Twelve biogeographic regions are represented. 1. Jura and sides, 2. Geneva Lake, 3. High Rhine, 4. West-Midland, 5. East-Midland, 6. Prealps, 7. Northern Alps, 8. Western Central Alps, 9. Eastern Central Alps, 10. Engadin, 11. Southern Alps, 12. Southern Ticino. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

landscape of agricultural subsidies. Finally, we discuss our results in the context of the regulatory framework and suggest ways to better engage farmers in conserving agrobiodiversity.

2. Methods

Two approaches were used to study the farmer’s participation in the ISP: governmental systematic national census data derived from the AGIS (Agrarpolitisches Informationssystem) system and a country-wide online survey.

2.1. Sample selection and agri-environmental metrics

Ecogeographic and farming-related data were selected from the AGIS database on a subset of 37’587 farms hosting permanent grassland and thus potential *in situ* surfaces (out of 47’719 farms in Switzerland in 2023, FOAG, 2023). The surfaces were coded in the Swiss information system under the following numbers: 613, “other permanent meadows without pasture”; 616, “pasture” and 625, “wooden pastures” (FOAG, 2022). Notably, surfaces were not eligible for selection if they were included in any other AES program. Farms from the administrative region Valais were excluded as it is the only canton not participating in the program (Kägi et al., 2023). The data were anonymised and divided into two distinct subsets based on their participation in the program (907 participants in total). The ecogeographic data allowed us to discriminate the farm size, 26 administrative regions (usually referred to as cantons), six altitudinal zones (valley, hillside, mountain 1-4), and twelve ecogeographic regions (Fig. 1). The farming data indicate whether the farm is managed under organic conditions, sixteen various farm types and the proportion of ECA in the farm (either “lower” Quality I or “higher” Quality II). All these variables were extracted from the national census performed by the Federal Office for Agriculture (FOAG, 2024). To analyse the extent to which these “farm descriptors” are associated with the ISP participation, we used a generalized linear model (GLM), an extension of classical linear regression that allows response variables that do not necessarily follow a normal distribution to be processed (Table 2). The response variable corresponds to participation in the ISP program (binary variable), which follows a binomial distribution. The model applied thus enables the estimation of the influence of predictors — in this case, altitudinal zone, biogeographical region, and farm size — on the probability of participating in the program (Table 2).

2.2. Survey design

The survey was structured to explore the farmers’ motivations for participating in the ISP. Fifteen items were rated on a 1: strongly disagree to 5: strongly agree Likert scale (DeVellis and Thorpe, 2021) by the participating farmers (questionnaire A, Fig. 2A) and fourteen by those who did not participate in the program (questionnaire B, Fig. 2B). Using two separate questionnaires maximised the response rate by

Table 1
Characteristics of the farms participating in the ISP according to the data from the national survey AGIS. *Total represents the eligible farms to the program, i.e. that host surfaces of interest with forage crops outside the conventionally subsidised surfaces. Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed on pairwise comparison and the p-value was shown accordingly.

Variables	Total*	ISP	Significance
Farm number	37’782	980	
Average size (ha)	29,59	37,78	t-test p < 2.2 ^{e-16}
Median size (ha)	24,60	31,62	
Average % Q1	15,01	25,99	Wilcoxon p < 2.2 ^{e-16}
Average % Q2	6,43	13,98	Wilcoxon p < 2.2 ^{e-16}
Organic farming (%)	18,38	36,72	X ² p < 2.2 ^{e-16}
Extensive surfaces (%)	10,62	16,88	X ² p = 0.05463
Intensive surfaces (%)	34,44	48,31	X ² p < 2.2 ^{e-16}

Table 2

Geographical characteristics of the farms participating in the ISP. The two most even categories, the hill zone and the Northern Alps were used as a reference to run a generalized linear model. We ran a generalized linear model that simultaneously evaluated the effects of the altitudinal zone, biogeographical region, and total farm surface (INSITU ~ ZONE + BIOGEO_REGION + tot surface). This model was compared to simpler models, each considering only one variable at a time. The model including all three variables had the lowest residual deviance. Administrative denomination of zones according to the Federal Office for Agriculture was used: valley, hillside, mountain 1 to 4 of increasing altitude and steepness (FOAG, 2023). Locations of participating farms were tested according to their location among six altitudinal zones (italic) and twelve biogeographic areas (bold). Significance: *Pr < 0.05, **<0.01, ***<0.001.

Variables	Estimate	Std. Error	Z value	Pr
<i>Int./Hillside/Northern Alps</i>	-3.914	1.517 ^{e-1}	-25.798	<2 ^{e-16} ***
<i>Mountain 1</i>	8.993e-2	1.451 ^{e-1}	0.620	0.53
<i>Mountain 2</i>	3.25e-1	1.366 ^{e-1}	2.379	0,01738 *
<i>Mountain 3</i>	3.224 ^{e-2}	1.661 ^{e-1}	0.194	0.84611
<i>Mountain 4</i>	-5.447e-2	1.824 ^{e-1}	-0.299	0.76520
<i>Valley</i>	-3.257 ^{e-1}	1.209 ^{e-1}	-2.694	0.00706 **
Engadin	1.717	2.370 ^{e-1}	7.244	4.36 ^{e-13} ***
Geneva lake	-1.037	5.202 ^{e-1}	-1.994	0.04617 *
High Rhine	4.87 ^{e-2}	2.432 ^{e-1}	0.200	0.84123
Jura	2.086 ^{e-1}	1.417 ^{e-1}	1.472	0.14096
East-Central Alps	1.570	1.446 ^{e-1}	11.589	<2 ^{e-16} ***
Eastern Midland	3.846	1.911 ^{e-1}	2.660	0.0078 **
Northern Ticino	1.992	2.976 ^{e-1}	10.420	<2 ^{e-16} ***
Southern Ticino	2.946 ^{e-1}	1.427 ^{e-1}	0.990	0.3222
Pre-Alps	-4.217 ^{e-1}	1.623 ^{e-1}	-2.956	0.00312 **
West-Central Alps	-8.360	1.823e-1	-0.053	0.9575
West-Midland	-1.1	1.826 ^{e-1}	-6.022	1.72 ^{e-9} ***

avoiding survey fatigue in a highly solicited population, and specified for each category the detailed components of their underlying motivations. The item-scale for participants and non-participants gathers information on practical outcomes of the programme implementation, followed by “belief”-items assessing the farmers’ intrinsic motivations towards (non-) participation and their perceptions of others’ opinions and future generations. If the farmers participated, additional questions were asked about *in situ* surface management (fertilisation, invasive weed management and herbicide treatment).

2.3. Survey validation

The survey’s content validity index (CVI) was calculated based on feedback from five experts (Polit et al., 2007). Experts were asked to rate clarity (0 = not clear/1 = clear) and relevance on a four-point scale (1 = not relevant, 2 = somewhat relevant, 3 = quite relevant, 4 = highly relevant) for each item. The item-level CVI was computed as the number of experts giving a rating of either 3 or 4, divided by the number of experts – that is, the proportion in agreement about relevance (Polit et al., 2007). All items with clarity equal to 1 and relevance greater than 0.8 have been kept unchanged. If the relevance was rated 0.5 or less, the item was removed. Items that were rated unclear have been reformulated and retested. Due to the expert panel involved, the validation was performed in both French and German versions, and the validated version was later translated into Italian.

2.4. Data collection

Eligible participants were anonymously recruited online using LimeSurvey (Gabel et al., 2018b; Home et al., 2014; Stoeckli et al., 2017). Farmers who participated in the online survey received a comprehensive written study description at the beginning of the survey. By clicking the “Next” button to enter the survey, they indicated their

Fig. 2. Motivations underlying farmer's participation in the ISP. A. Results of questionnaire A, motivations for the farmers to participate in the ISP, n = 293. B. Barriers preventing farmers from participating in the ISP, n = 730. A Likert scale was used to evaluate each item from 1 (strongly disagree, red) to 5 (strongly agree, green). The bar plots show the number of respondents for each scale level, the mean and standard deviation (SD) are displayed on the right. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

willingness to voluntarily participate in the study, providing informed consent for an anonymous online survey. The pre-validated questionnaire was sent in German, French and Italian. Data were collected from November 6, 2024 until January 6, 2025. In total, 1'023 farmers took part in the survey, of which 293 participated in the program and 730 did not participate. To precisely capture the reasons for the participation choices, two specific questionnaires for each subgroup were designed. The term "farmer" used here is comprehensively gender-diverse.

2.5. Data analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using R version 4.3.2 (R Core Team, 2023). The dataset was divided into two subsets: one containing data from farms that participated in the ISP, and another including farms that responded to the survey but did not participate in the ISP. A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on the questionnaire responses to reduce potential collinearity by transforming correlated variables into a set of uncorrelated principal components, followed by a varimax rotation to enhance interpretability. To assess data adequacy, we followed the guidelines provided in the psych package manual (Revelle, 2024). Statistics are summarised in Tables 4 and 5. For each subset, two principal components were retained and associated with categories based on the items that exhibited the strongest correlations with each component.

We then analysed the relationship between the median score of each item category and various eco-geographical data from the national survey. For binary variables (e.g., "organic farm" and "habitat connectivity"), a Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon test was used. For categorical variables (e.g., "farm type" and "altitudinal zone"), a Kruskal-Wallis test was performed, followed by a post hoc analysis to identify significant differences between categories. Finally, for continuous, non-linearly distributed variables (e.g., "percentage of Q1/Q2 area"), a Spearman correlation test was conducted. These three statistical tests were implemented using functions from the stats package in R.

3. Results

3.1. Remaining potentials for the ISP to cover the entire diversity

Three years after the program started, 1418 surfaces were included in the ISP nationally, representing 1592 ha and originating from 907 farms (Fig. 1). The distribution of the surfaces included in the ISP across the various eco-geographical regions has been analysed previously (Kägi et al., 2023). The overlap between the estimated genetic diversity of the target forage species (and their wild relatives) and the extent of coverage by the ISP is not comprehensive compared to the initial objective of the program: conserving the largest portion of forage crop species genetic diversity (Kägi et al., 2023). Despite some efforts to fill this gap, the ISP

Table 3

Farming profile of the farms participating in the ISP. The farming type most likely participating in the ISP was analysed by a generalized linear model. Parameters like the fact whether the farm is organic and has ecological compensation areas (ECA) of quality I or II as well as eleven farm types were tested. The category “Breeding” as the most even category was chosen as a reference. Significance *Pr < 0.05, **<0.01, ***<0.001.

Variables	Estimate	Std. Er.	Z value	Pr
(Intercept)/Breeding	-3.943	2.276 ^{e-1}	-17.326	<2 ^{e-16} ***
Organic farming	7.406 ^{e-1}	7.576 ^{e-2}	9.775	<2 ^{e-16} ***
ECA Quality I	2.612 ^{e-6}	7.514 ^{e-7}	3.477	0.00050 ***
ECA Quality II	2.494 ^{e-6}	1.134 ^{e-6}	2.198	0.02791 *
Cereals	-1.188	3.251 ^{e-1}	-3.375	0.00073 ***
Combined Other crops	-3.248 ^{e-1}	2.468 ^{e-1}	-1.316	0.18819 ***
Combined Milk cows/ Cereals	-5.748 ^{e-1}	3.130 ^{e-1}	-1.837	0.06628
Combined Mother cows	-4.619 ^{e-1}	2.999 ^{e-1}	-1.540	0.1235
Combined breeding	-3.207 ^{e-1}	2.50 ^{e-1}	-1.243	0.2138
Milk production	2.689 ^{e-2}	2.354 ^{e-1}	-0.114	0.9090
Mother cows	3.168 ^{e-1}	2.409 ^{e-1}	1.315	0.1885
Horses/Sheep/Goats	-4.45 ^{e-1}	2.669 ^{e-1}	-1.669	0.0951
Beef cattle mixed	6.475 ^{e-2}	2.479 ^{e-1}	0.269	0.7939
Special crops	-1.591	3.918 ^{e-1}	-4.060	4.91 ^{e-5} ***

Table 4

Rotated Component Matrix for the variables underlying motivations to participation in the ISP (Questionnaire A). Cronbach’s α: 0.841.

Items	Components	
	Principles	Modalities
The program requirements are easy to implement and not too restrictive.	0.218	0.631
I can get contributions for these plots.		0.710
I like the fact that participation is based on farmers’ initiative.		0.651
It allows me to make a less productive plot of land more profitable.		0.405
Complement the environmental measures already in place on my farm.	0.591	0.309
Important to make my farm’s genetic diversity available for plant breeding.	0.708	0.191
I think that this contributes to the conservation and promotion of biodiversity.	0.757	0.161
I am interested in conserving the genetic diversity of forage plants.	0.721	-0.213
I think it’s a useful and effective way of preparing for climate change.	0.605	0.154
It fits in with my farm’s philosophy.	0.771	0.147
Promoting and conserving the genetic diversity of forage plants is one of ag’s responsibilities.	0.705	0.101
I think that conserving the genetic diversity of forage plants is useful for future generations.	0.769	
I want to contribute to a good image of agriculture.	0.361	0.437
I am proud of my acreage and I’m pleased that my good work is being recognised.	0.576	0.416
SS loadings	4.51	2.12
Proportion variance	0.32	0.15
Cumulative variance	0.32	0.47
Proportion explained	0.68	0.32
Cumulative proportion	0.68	1.00

Table 5

Rotated Component Matrix for the variables underlying barriers to participation in the ISP (Questionnaire B). Cronbach’s α: 0.847.

Items	Components	
	Constraints	Accessibility
I didn’t think my land could meet the selection criteria.		0.603
I don’t have the time to look into it.	0.409	0.451
It was not explained clearly enough.	0.189	0.775
It’s not clear how access rights to plants for research and breeding will be granted.	0.228	0.784
I find the participation questionnaire too long and complicated to fill in.	0.441	0.596
It restricts my growing methods too much.	0.713	
It is difficult for me to make a long-term commitment.	0.658	0.122
I don’t get paid enough for taking part.	0.582	0.235
The floristic survey is too expensive.	0.642	0.245
I find the ban on overseeding in the event of damage too restrictive.	0.66	
It conflicts with the environmental measures already in place on my farm.	0.51	0.288
I don’t think this program is useful.	0.638	0.157
I don’t feel concerned by the subject.	0.522	0.201
I have heard negative feedback from participants in the program.	0.39	0.132
SS loadings	3.67	2.44
Proportion variance	0.26	0.17
Cumulative variance	0.26	0.44
Proportion explained	0.60	0.40
Cumulative proportion	0.60	1.00

still does not fully capture the potential niche suitability of the target forage species associations, and consequently, probably does not reflect their diversity sufficiently (Kägi et al., 2023). Therefore, it is essential better to understand the basis for the distribution of ISP surfaces and to characterise more precisely which farmers have participated and why.

3.2. Profiling the farms participating in the ISP

A detailed analysis of the national census enabled us to map precisely the proportion of eligible farms to the program, specifically those with grassland surfaces that meet the program’s entry criteria. While 78.7 % of all Swiss farms could theoretically participate, only about 2 % effectively did (907 farms participating). There is potential for more participants to join in the following years. The national census data also provides a precise snapshot of the specificities of the farms already in the program. Farms participating in the ISP are tendentially larger, with an average surface of 37.78 instead of 29.59 ha (*t*-test *p* < 2.2^{e-16}), with more ECA (13.98 % Quality II instead of 6.43 % for the eligible farms, Wilcoxon *p* < 2.2^{e-16}) and more likely to practice organic farming (36.72 % instead of 18.38 %, *X*² test *p* < 2.2^{e-16}, Table 1). In addition, farms in the hills and valley regions were less likely to participate, and farms from Engadin and the Eastern Central Alps are better represented in the program (Table 2). The type of farming activity is also associated with participation in the program, with farms cultivating cereals or special crops less likely to participate (Table 3).

3.3. Drivers of the farmer’s participation in the ISP

Sending the questionnaire to all the eligible farms provided information on the general level of awareness of the farmers to the program. Only 41.4 % (1235 out of 2978) of the respondents had heard of the program before. A significant portion of farmers (42 %) learnt about the programme through local (cantonal) authorities, their agriculture advisor, or professional media (Supplementary Fig. 1).

Two validated questionnaires (A/participants and B/non-participants) were analysed independently using a Principal Component Analysis using the varimax algorithm that allows extraction of main

components structuring the variance across the item's questionnaires. Cronbach's α of 0.841 and 0.847 were calculated for questionnaires A/participants and B/non-participants respectively, which suggests adequate internal reliability. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) indexes were greater than 0.67 and 0.84, respectively, indicating that the data are suited to a factor analysis. One item in Questionnaire A with a KMO < 0.6 was removed from further analysis. The Bartlett Test of Sphericity was statistically significant ($p < 0.00001$) in both cases, and the absence of multicollinearity confirms sampling adequacy and suggests that the data are appropriate for a Principal Component Analysis. Significant components were used when more than two factors displayed loadings greater than 0.4 (Tables 4 and 5).

For questionnaire A/participants, two components emerged in the rotated component matrix, collectively explaining 47 % of the variance (Table 4). The first component, described as "Principles" focuses on values and choices that encompass more general aims or interests (such as climate change and future generations) that may be integrated into subjective norms in the TPB framework (Home et al., 2014). This component highlights conservation activities as a medium-to long-term benefit in response to a particular perception of farming activities. The second component relates to "Modalities" and includes items more directly associated with immediate accessibility and benefits that justify farmers' attitudes and reflect their intrinsic motivations (De Snoo et al., 2013; Gabel et al., 2018a). This component features some of the highest-scoring items: "I can get contributions for these plots" with an average Likert score of 4.63 ± 0.76 (Fig. 2A). Interestingly, although not statistically significant (with a component loading of -0.213), interest in the programme appears to be inversely correlated with the "Modalities" component (Table 4). This observation corresponds with two different approaches: conservationists versus productivists, as reported earlier (Home et al., 2014).

For questionnaire B/non-participants, two major components explained a cumulated 43 % of the variance for farmers who did not participate in the ISP (Table 5). The first component, "Constraints", explains that 26 % of the variance is centred around attitudinal parameters, such as the cost/benefit ratio being too unbalanced for the farmers to participate in the program (not enough subsidies, floristic survey too expensive or over-sowing ban considered too constraining). The second component, "Accessibility" indicates a widespread lack of clarity about the program, its scope, modalities and access (Table 5), with some of the highest scores compared to other items ("it was not explained clearly enough" with an average Likert score of 3.48 ± 1.2). This latest component, representing the non-participant's motivations, aligns with perceived behavioural controls of the TPB that were also reported to conflict with other AES (Home et al., 2014). The non-participants appear to doubt that the ISP can achieve the desired outcome and feel they are not in a position to implement it. This may be partly due to a lack of relevant information available or a lack of clarity and flexibility in the modalities.

In an additional step, we assessed whether some eco-geographical features of the participating farms reported in the national survey (Tables 1–3) could be correlated with some specific motivational components resulting from the farmer's ISP poll (Tables 4 and 5). The most significant correlations are illustrated in Fig. 4. Briefly, organic farmers appear to value significantly "Principles" compared to other farmers (Wilcoxon test, $p = 0.0327$), while being less sensitive to "Constraints" and "Accessibility" ($p = 4.151e-6$ and $p = 0.02469$, respectively). Similarly, the percentage of ECA of quality I and quality II on a farm is positively correlated with the "Principles" component (Spearman's Rho = 0.1301, $p = 0.02616$ and Rho = 0.1161, $p = 0.0475$ respectively). Taken together, it appears that participation in the ISP is facilitated by the pre-existing participation to any other AES (particularly to organic labels, Table 1).

3.4. Agronomical specifications of the *in situ* surfaces

Farmers who participated in the ISP were subsequently asked in the survey to describe their agricultural practices related to the *in situ* surfaces. In particular, 90.3 % of the farmers use fertilisers on their *in situ* surface, 50 % slurry, 34 % manure and 10 % inorganic forms with an average dose (when possibly known) of 17 kg nitrogen per ha (Fig. 3A–C). The surfaces are usually mowed on average two to three times a year when not grazed (Fig. 3E). Relatively few herbicides were used on *in situ* surfaces (less than 5 % of the surfaces, Fig. 3D), while about 10 % of the *in situ* surfaces were confronted with exotic invasive species (Fig. 3F). These complementary data provide a more precise sketch of the farming practice under the ISP and the extent to which the compliance is respected.

4. Discussion

4.1. Eco-geographical constraints to participation in an AES

With a maximum threshold of 2750 ha to be allocated by the federal authorities, there is still room in the ISP for additional surfaces to be integrated (Kägi et al., 2023). The most obvious question is the reason why, three years after inception, the entire allocated money and surface quotas have not been distributed. The analysis of national survey data reveals a significant impact of eco-geographical constraints on the farmers' participation in the ISP. Farms tend to get larger as altitude increases, contrary to the land use intensity (lower altitude commonly means more intensive land use). This situation creates more space and opportunities for farmers in higher altitudes to "invest" in the program. Given that farmers typically act rationally, it is not surprising to have lower participation rates in regions characterized by smaller and more intensive farms, such as valley areas predominantly managed by cereal or specialized crop producers (Table 3). These eco-geographical constraints may influence farming choices, usually favouring organic farming or more extensive land use, and must be considered for any ECA. These observations frame the potential impacts of the policy framework or norms used in farming practices overall (Westerink et al., 2024). From a conservation policy perspective, lower altitude agroecosystems, which tend to be more intensive, are more difficult to access and may therefore be targeted by additional dedicated efforts and measures to achieve sufficient levels of agrobiodiversity.

4.2. The ISP through the lens of the theory of planned behaviour

Considering the limitations linked to the eco-geographical constraints, understanding the motivations for a farmer to participate in a program like the ISP remains essential. Indeed, a large body of scholars studied the role of behavioural factors in participating in AES (Canessa et al., 2024; Schaub et al., 2023). Focusing on the ISP, we demonstrated that a specific worldview influences farmers' attitudes towards participating in an AES. Most participants are driven by "principles" that go beyond their immediate interests (Table 4). The ISP, as voluntary and non-vital (maximum 900 CHF per year) to the financial stability of the farm, appears well fitted within other existing ECAs, being simply a kind of extension of existing farming practices. The antagonistic relationship often reported in the literature between conservation vs. production is less pronounced here (Home et al., 2014), while the modalities and immediate benefits to the farmers are drivers of the participation. Farmers who already participate in other AES, have more ECA surfaces than average, or use organic farming are more likely to participate in the ISP.

There is a widespread feeling of responsibility towards conserving genetic diversity among farmers, and they feel empowered by their participation. Many farmers articulated the need to anticipate climate change and their readiness to prepare for this change:

Fig. 3. Agronomic metrics on land management on *in situ* surfaces provided by the participants of the ISP. A. Number of fertilisers application per season, B. Type of fertilisers used, C. Amount of nitrogen used (in kg/ha), knowing manure’s estimation were generally excluded, D. Usage of herbicide on the *in situ* surface, E. Mowing frequency on the *in situ* surfaces per season, F. Occurrence of neophytes on the *in situ* surfaces.

Fig. 4. The eco-geographical and motivational factors framing the participation in the ISP. Following the theory of planned behaviour, a farmer’s motivation to participate in the ISP is framed by attitudes, perceived behavioural control and subjective norms. Arrows represent correlations between eco-geographical factors and components of motivation. Solid lines indicate the responses of participants in the *in situ* program, while dashed lines represent the responses of non-participants. Metrics of the correlations: 1. $X^2 = 20.521$, $p = 0.0246$, Cereal, cows and combined farms are significantly more correlated to constraints than other types of farming, 2. $X^2 = 16.141$, $p = 0.0064$, the valley is significantly more correlated to constraints than other regions, 3. Non-participant, Wilcoxon $p = 4.151e^{-6}$, 4. Spearman $\rho = -0.0914$ $p = 0.0171$, 5. Wilcoxon $p = 0.0157$, 6. Wilcoxon $p = 0.0327$, 7. Spearman $\rho = 0.1161$ $p = 0.0475$, 8. Spearman $\rho = 0.1301$, $p = 0.0261$.

“During storms or heavy precipitations etc., it is clear self-adapted, diverse meadows are much more resilient”

“We should be prepared to do something that will benefit future generations”

“I participated {in the ISP} because I think the climate is going quicker than breeding programs”

(Comments collected from the survey)

There is a more noticeable perceived behavioural control among farmers who do not participate, especially regarding accessibility issues to the program. Overall, when examining through the lenses of the TPB, it seems that attitudes and subjective norms are key factors in the

farmer’s decision to participate. While it remains clear that financial incentives are necessary (Gabel et al., 2018b; Siebert et al., 2006), farmers’ motivations are nonetheless more complex (Brown et al., 2021; Mills et al., 2018), particularly in a voluntary scheme with relatively low contributions as the ISP. Participants generally utilise non-compulsory programs as opportunities to valorise their farming activity. There often seems to be a relatively large degree of interpretation and perception regarding the aims and impact of the program on agrobiodiversity conservation. For instance, an example of a comment: “This contribution does not promote extensification of meadows, but rather their natural and appropriate use”.

Most non-participants still find the program interesting. Non-participants have a broader negative attitude, not just towards this

specific program but towards more general farming constraints and the regulatory “complex” at large. Our analysis through the lens of the TPB has shown a central influence of attitudinal components in both participants and non-participants (Fig. 4). This indicates that, regardless of considering the *ISP* design, many underlying values and norms (pre-) condition the farmer’s decision to participate in the program. This is very much in line with the social challenge behind the improvement of AES generally reported (De Snoo et al., 2013). Some elements of the motivation could be correlated with specific components associated with the farm characteristics (arrows in Fig. 4). For example, the impact of organic farming and increasing AES surfaces (QI and QII) was correlated to the “Principles”/subjective norms components. Farmers already participating in AES appear to be better integrated into the “instrument complex” and, therefore, are less affected by “Constraints” (Fig. 4). This suggests a strong path-dependency for acceptance of AES measures and a very heterogeneous integration of farmers into the AES policy complex. In other words, the more a farmer is embedded in the production/policy system, the more resilient he/she is to new changes. The non-participation in AES may be a better indicator of a farmer’s ability to fit within a policy system rather than a somewhat oversimplified dichotomy between productivist and conservationist attitudes.

4.3. Fostering farmer’s motivations in the agricultural policy complex

The *ISP* has not appeared in an institutional vacuum. The complexity and inefficiency of the agro-environmental policy regime are frequently criticised (Pe’er et al., 2022). While there is room for improvement, some monitoring data quantitatively show a degree of efficiency in conserving agrobiodiversity (Klaus et al., 2023; Meier et al., 2024). Our results also indicate a high acceptance of the new subsidy program among farmers who already integrate AES as part of their daily farming practices. Motivations of farmers, particularly in more intensive lowlands have been assessed and called for more flexibility in the ECA’s implementation (Home et al., 2014; Niskanen et al., 2021). The *ISP* is widely accepted as a “bottom-up” approach, which suggests a need for empowering farmers in their decision-making. Maybe surprisingly, the complex set of rules already dictated by the other AES and subsidies seems well internalised by the participating farmers, and this has facilitated the inception of the *ISP*. Farmers within labels (such as organic farming) have easier access to pertinent information about existing subsidies (Gabel et al., 2018a). In contrast, the lack of awareness of the program and the demand for more communication on the importance of agrobiodiversity highlight another responsibility of the authorities to not only provide equal access to the schemes but also to recognize the inequalities in the ability of various farmers to engage with the program (Fig. 4).

Considering the relatively good acceptance of the *ISP*, a similar approach could be a promising model for other AES (Barnes et al., 2013). This appears to be at least partly related to its relatively low administrative burden. Meanwhile, it may also reflect a lack of ambition in the programme, being simply too permissive: an easy target for low-yield surfaces and thus an “easy bonus” within the subsidies landscape, as seen with other instruments before (Batáry et al., 2015; Delvaux et al., 1999).

4.4. The *ISP* as a blueprint for grassland conservation?

It is essential to remember that *in situ* surfaces are (semi-)intensive surfaces, with active fertilisation and mowing (Fig. 3) and logically host only a relatively small subset of forage-related species (Kägi et al., 2023). The largest genepool of grassland species remains under the scope of other grasslands AES with more restrictive measures in place (Kampmann et al., 2012). We have shown here that from a conservation point of view, the bidding system used for the *ISP* raises the issue of comprehensively covering the various altitudinal and eco-geographical

conditions that may host the broadest range of genetic diversity. This is a model that may also be interesting for conservation under climate change constraints (Pearman et al., 2024). The bottom-up approach of the *ISP*, which allows farmers to freely decide where to locate conserved surfaces, raises some governance issues that still need to be solved (Kägi et al., 2023). To cover all targeted populations (i.e., the most threatened populations or those most representative of genetic diversity), it is necessary to focus on a subset of surfaces specifically at the local level. The ambiguity between bottom-up participation and comprehensiveness in conservation needs to be addressed. In any case, a possible extension of the *ISP* to other species, like crop wild relatives, to other grassland surfaces or threatened species is being considered (Petitpierre et al., 2023). We also show that the *ISP* targets specific surfaces at the margin between extensive and intensive farming. A small payment from the program may help maintain the cost/benefit balance in favour of conservation, often preventing the surface from being intensified or over-sown with commercial seeds. The issue of fluctuating yield has been a recurring theme in the survey comments and is expected to become even more critical in a changing climate (Korell et al., 2024).

For any similar program to succeed, local authorities and controllers must be well aware of the stakes and keep close contact with farmers. Sharing information widely aims to create a community of practice on grassland that dynamically utilises and conserves its genepool as an essential ecosystem service. Although information may not always be central to participation in an AES (Schaub et al., 2023), there is a clear demand for increased outreach activities regarding forage and grassland diversity, both within the farming community and towards the public.

5. Conclusion

The relative success of the *ISP*’s nationwide expansion and farmers’ generally positive attitudes towards participation suggest that many avenues remain unexplored for developing effective AES. Further research is required to explore how farmer-centred/bottom-up approaches can achieve substantial compliance and high-quality surfaces in the long term. Our data suggest that the main problem with voluntary AES programs may not rely on the farmer’s motivation but, in large part, on how the limits to participation are perceived. Interestingly, the extent to which the program may or may not allow an improvement in symbolic capital and reputation gain: “giving a good image” is also important for the farmer to participate (Burton et al., 2008). Difficulties in accessing coherent information often become the central limit to participation. Improving farmers’ willingness to participate in conservation may be a social challenge (De Snoo et al., 2013), but it is also a governance challenge. The need to improve communication has also been correlated to a lower perceived administrative burden for other instruments (Mack et al., 2019).

More and better ECA surfaces are needed to achieve comprehensive conservation of agrobiodiversity (Stöckli et al., 2024). However, the question of how best to support ECA’s quality and their contribution to the agroecosystem resilience while keeping the economic stability of the farms can only be answered on a case-by-case level (Schulz et al., 2024). For the *ISP*, the following steps will be to continue increasing its participation rate while also assessing its impact on the gene pool of the targeted grassland species. Fostering plant diversity on semi-natural grasslands can promote more sustainable farming practices, which in turn can affect yield and revenues (Schaub et al., 2020). Sufficient levels of diversity can only be preserved if gene pools are accessible and conserved through instruments like the *ISP*. Target 10 of the Global Biodiversity Framework calls for agricultural areas to be “managed through the sustainable use of biodiversity” (CBD, 2022). This ambitious goal can only be realised if the custodians of agricultural lands, the farmers, are empowered to undertake such management.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Morgane Lambert: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christina Kägi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Antoine Guisan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Blaise Petitpierre:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sylvain Aubry:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many farmers and experts who took some of their precious time to make this study possible, Alexander Wenger for facilitating access to the AGIS data and colleague experts for validating the survey. The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policies or positions of the FOAG, the UNIL or any funders. The research has been supported by the Horizon project COUSIN funded by the EU (European Union), the Swiss State Secretariat for Research and Innovation (grant n°22.0412) and the UKRI (United Kingdom Research and Innovation).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.103938>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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